

Studies in Fluorochalkones. Part I. Synthesis of Chalkones from Fluorohydroxyacetophenones

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Various chalkones, derived from 2-hydroxy-5-fluoro-, 2-hydroxy-3-chloro-5-fluoro-, and 2-hydroxy-3-bromo-5-fluoro-acetophenones are described. The chalkones formed have been converted into their dibromides and 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazones.

Although a variety of chalkones have been studied by various workers, very little seems to be known regarding fluorine-substituted chalkones. In view of the reported biologically interesting properties of certain fluorohydroxy ketones^{1,2}, we thought it worthwhile to study the chalkones derived from some of these ketones. We have been led to this field by the fact that the grouping $\text{C}=\text{C}-\text{CO}-$, characteristic of these chalkones, is also present in many naturally occurring antibiotics and may be responsible for their antibacterial activity³. This bactericidal activity of chalkones has also been reported by Jeney *et al.*⁴ and Minorn *et al.*⁵.

Keeping these observations in view, several fluorine-substituted chalkones have been synthesised by condensing 2-hydroxy-5-fluoro-, 2-hydroxy-3-chloro-5-fluoro-, and 2-hydroxy-3-bromo-5-fluoro-acetophenones with various aldehydes. The fluorohydroxy-acetophenones were prepared by the Fries reaction of appropriate esters.

The chalkones were treated with bromine in acetic acid when their dibromides were obtained. The latter, when treated with potassium iodide in acetone, were debrominated and the original chalkones were regenerated.

EXPERIMENTAL

p-Fluoroanisole was prepared by the method of English *et al.*⁶ from *p*-anisidine (60 g.); yield 28 g.

p-Fluorophenol was obtained by demethylation of *p*-fluoroanisole (28 g.), b. p. 184-86°; yield 16 g.

1. Bun Hoī *et al.*, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1953, **18**, 910; 1954, **19**, 1617.
2. Joshi and Bahel, *this Journal*, 1960, **37**, 687.
3. Marrian *et al.*, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1947, 1419.
4. *Zentr. Bact. parasitenk. Abt. I. Org.*, 1955, **163**, 791.
5. *J. Agril. Chem. Soc. Japan*, 1954, **28**, 791.
6. *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1940, **62**, 350.
7. Finger *et al.*, *ibid.*, 1959, **81**, 94.

2-Chloro-4-fluorophenol was prepared by bubbling chlorine gas (27 g.) into *p*-fluorophenol (84 g.) in presence of iron filings at room temperature for 7½ hrs., b.p. 60-62° (0.1-1 mm); Finger *et al.*⁸ report b. p. 88° (4mm).

2-Bromo-4-fluorophenol was obtained by treatment of bromine (36 g.) with *p*-fluorophenol (25 g.) in CS₂ medium, b. p. 59-60° (0.5 mm). Finger *et al.*⁸ report b. p. 89° (1mm).

Esters of the above phenols were prepared by treating the phenols (0.1 *M*) with acetyl chloride (0.1 *M*) in presence of magnesium ribbon (1.29 g.), using anhydrous benzene (25 ml) as the solvent. The esters were isolated by the usual method and then subjected to the Fries rearrangement by heating the ester (0.06 *M*) and anhydrous aluminium chloride (0.1 *M*) for 2½ hours at 130°.

2-Hydroxy-5-fluoroacetophenone, 2-hydroxy-3-chloro-5-fluoroacetophenone, and 2-hydroxy-3-bromo-5-fluoroacetophenone were isolated and purified in the usual manner. Their m. p. or b. p. corresponded to that previously recorded¹.

General Method of Chalkone Formation.—An ethanolic solution of the appropriate ketone (0.02 *M*) was mixed with equimolecular amounts of the requisite aldehyde (0.02 *M*) and a solution of 30 ml. of 40% KOH was carefully added to the mixture with shaking. The reaction mixture was allowed to stand for a period ranging from 2 to 7 days with occasional shaking. It was then poured into ice and acidified with dilute HCl. The chalkone was collected and crystallised from ethanol.

In case of *p*-hydroxybenzaldehyde (0.02 *M*) and salicylaldehyde (0.02 *M*), 30 ml of 20% KOH solution was used^{10,11}.

A semisolid was obtained during condensation of 2-hydroxy-5-fluoroacetophenone with *p*-hydroxybenzaldehyde. This was taken in ethanol-ether mixture and kept overnight at room temperature when the chalkone crystallised.

In the condensation of 2-hydroxy-3-bromo-5-fluoroacetophenone and benzaldehyde, a 10% alkali solution (30 ml) was used and the reaction mixture heated gently at 60° for 2 hours¹². The various chalkones prepared are listed in Table I. These chalkones have been characterised through their 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazones. In a few cases, the fluorine content was also estimated.

Dibromide Formations.—The chalkone, dissolved in acetic acid, was treated with bromine and the clear red solution allowed to stand for nearly 24 hrs. at room temperature. It was diluted with water, the precipitate filtered, washed with water, and recrystallised from ethanol¹³. These dibromides are recorded in Table II and have been mainly characterised through their 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazones.

8. Finger, Private communication.

9. Sen and Tiwari, *this Journal*, 1952, 29, 421.

10. Kohler and Chadwell, "Org. Syntheses", II, 1922, p. 1.

11. Weygand and Schacher, *Ber.*, 1935, 58B, 227.

12. Schraufstatter and Deutsch, *Ber.*, 1948, 81, 489.

13. Shah and Parikh, *this Journal*, 1959, 36, 726.

TABLE I

I. Chalkones from 2-hydroxy-5-fluoracetophenone (I: X=H).

Aldehyde.	Chalkones.	Colour.	M.P.	%Fluorine.		2,4-Dinitrophenylhydrazones		%Nitrogen.	
				Found.	Reqd.	Colour.	Formula.	Found.	Reqd.
1. Benzaldehyde	2'-Hydroxy-Ch* (C ₁₅ H ₁₁ O ₂ F)	Yellow	83-84°	7.76	7.85	Orange	C ₂₁ H ₁₅ O ₃ N ₄ F	13.21	13.27
2. Anisaldehyde	2'-Hydroxy-4-methoxy-Ch (C ₁₆ H ₁₃ O ₃ F)	Brownish yellow	114-15°	7.20	6.98	Dark orange	C ₂₂ H ₁₇ O ₆ N ₄ F	12.26	12.38
3. Salicylaldehyde	2',2'-Dihydroxy-Ch (C ₁₅ H ₁₁ O ₃ F)	Yellow	166-67°	7.41	7.36	Do	C ₂₁ H ₁₅ O ₆ N ₄ F	12.30	12.76
4. Piperonal	2'-Hydroxy-3,4-methylenedioxy-Ch (C ₁₆ H ₁₁ O ₄ F)	Do	146°	6.71	6.64	Orange	C ₂₁ H ₁₅ O ₇ N ₄ F	11.82	12.01
5. Vanillin	2',4'-Dihydroxy-3-methoxy-Ch (C ₁₆ H ₁₃ O ₄ F)	Brownish yellow	148°	6.72	6.59	Dark brown	C ₂₂ H ₁₇ O ₇ N ₄ F	11.24	11.66
6. <i>p</i> -Dimethylaminobenzaldehyde	2'-Hydroxy-4-dime-thylamino-Ch (C ₁₇ H ₁₆ O ₂ NF)	Yellow	140°	..	..	Orange	C ₂₃ H ₂₀ O ₃ N ₅ F	11.06	12.64
7. <i>p</i> -Hydroxybenzaldehyde	2',4'-Dihydroxy-Ch (C ₁₅ H ₁₁ O ₃ F)	Reddish orange	165°	..	..	Do	C ₂₁ H ₁₅ O ₆ N ₄ F	12.56	12.78
8. Anisaldehyde	2'-Hydroxy-3'-chloro-4-methoxy-Ch (C ₁₆ H ₁₀ O ₃ ClF)	Brownish yellow	38-38°	..	..	Reddish orange	C ₂₂ H ₁₆ O ₆ N ₄ ClF	11.35	11.51

II. Chalkones from 2-hydroxy-3-chloro-5-fluoroacetophenone (X=Cl).

TABLE I (contd.)

Aldehyde.	Chalkone.	Colour.	M.P.	%Fluorine.		%Nitrogen.				
				Found.	Reqd.	Found.	Reqd.			
9. Piperonal	2'-Hydroxy-3'-chloro-3,4-methylendioxy-Ch (C ₁₆ H ₁₀ O ₄ ClF)	Yellow	176-77°	..	..	162°	Orange	C ₂₂ H ₁₄ O ₇ N ₄ ClF	10.98	11.18
10. <i>p</i> -Dimethyl-aminobenzaldehyde	2'-Hydroxy-3'-chloro-4-dimethylamino-Ch (C ₁₇ H ₁₅ O ₂ NCIF)	Dark orange	52°	..	..	214°	Do	C ₂₃ H ₁₉ O ₅ N ₃ ClF	11.34	11.53
III. Chalkones from 2-hydroxy-3-bromo-5-fluoroacetophenone (X=Br).										
11. Benzaldehyde	2'-Hydroxy-3'-bromo-Ch (C ₁₅ H ₁₁ O ₃ BrF)	Brownish yellow	118°	..	..	97-98°	Dark orange	C ₂₁ H ₁₄ O ₅ N ₄ BrF	10.08	11.17
12. Anisaldehyde	2'-Hydroxy-3'-bromo-4-methoxy-Ch (C ₁₆ H ₁₂ O ₃ BrF)	Pale yellow	128°	..	..	160°	Yellowish orange	C ₂₂ H ₁₆ O ₆ N ₄ BrF	10.43	10.54
13. Salicylaldehyde	2',3'-Dihydroxy-3'-bromo-Ch (C ₁₅ H ₁₀ O ₃ BrF)	Brownish yellow	113-15°	..	..	211°	Orange	C ₂₁ H ₁₄ O ₆ N ₄ BrF	10.72	10.83
14. Piperonal	2'-Hydroxy-3'-bromo-3,4-methylendioxy-Ch (C ₁₆ H ₁₀ O ₄ BrF)	Do	163°	..	..	162°	Dark brown	C ₂₂ H ₁₄ O ₇ N ₄ BrF	9.96	10.27
15. Vanillin	2',4'-Dihydroxy-3-methoxy-3'-bromo-Ch (C ₁₆ H ₁₀ O ₄ BrF)	Pale yellow	129°	..	..	196°	Orange	C ₂₂ H ₁₆ O ₇ N ₄ BrF	10.15	10.23
16. <i>p</i> -Dimethyl-aminobenzaldehyde	2'-Hydroxy-3'-bromo-4-dimethylamino-Ch (C ₁₇ H ₁₅ O ₂ NBrF)	Dark brown	130-31°	..	..	164-65°	Reddish brown	C ₂₃ H ₁₉ O ₅ N ₃ BrF	10.10	10.29

*Ch. denotes 5-fluorochalkone.

TABLE II
Dibromides.

Chalkones.	Colour.	M.P.	F ⁶⁹ Fluorine.		M.P.	2,4-Dinitrophenylhydrazones.		% Nitrogen Found.	Reqd.
			Found.	Reqd.		Colour.	Formula.		
1. 2'-Hydroxy-Ch* (C ₁₅ H ₁₁ O ₂ Br ₂ F)	Pale yellow	138-40°	4.80	4.72					
2. 2'-Hydroxy-4-methoxy-Ch (C ₁₆ H ₁₃ O ₃ Br ₂ F)	Do	67-00°	4.31	4.39					
3. 2',2'-Dihydroxy-Ch (C ₁₅ H ₁₁ O ₃ Br ₂ F)	Do	00°	4.60	4.54					
4. 2'-Hydroxy-3,4-methylenedioxy-Ch (C ₁₆ H ₁₁ O ₄ Br ₂ F)	Do	82-83°	4.30	4.26					
5. 2',4'-Dihydroxy-3-methoxy-Ch (C ₁₆ H ₁₃ O ₄ Br ₂ F)	Light brown	100-11°	4.28	4.24					
6. 2'-Hydroxy-4-dimethylamino-Ch (C ₁₇ H ₁₆ O ₂ NBr ₂ F)	Yellowish green	56°	..	..	130°	Orange	C ₂₃ H ₃₀ O ₅ N ₅ Br ₂ F	11.15	11.20
7. 2',4'-Dihydroxy-Ch (C ₁₅ H ₁₁ O ₃ Br ₂ F)	Chocolate	94-95°	..	..	99-100°	Do	C ₂₁ H ₁₅ O ₆ N ₄ Br ₂ F	9.29	9.36
8. 2'-Hydroxy-3'-chloro-4-methoxy-Ch (C ₁₆ H ₁₂ O ₃ Br ₂ ClF)	Yellow	78°	..	..	218°	Do	C ₂₂ H ₁₆ O ₆ N ₄ Br ₂ ClF	8.48	8.66
9. 2'-Hydroxy-3'-chloro-3,4-methylene-dioxy-Ch (C ₁₆ H ₁₀ O ₄ Br ₂ ClF)	Light yellow	68°	..	..	100°	Do	C ₂₂ H ₁₄ O ₇ N ₄ Br ₂ ClF	8.29	8.47
10. 2'-Hydroxy-3'-chloro-4-dimethylamino- violet Ch(C ₁₇ H ₁₅ O ₂ NBr ₂ ClF)	Dark violet	58-59°	..	..	110°	Dark brown	C ₂₃ H ₁₉ O ₃ N ₃ Br ₂ ClF	10.49	10.61
11. 2'-Hydroxy-3'-bromo-Ch (C ₁₅ H ₁₀ O ₂ Br ₃ F)	Light yellow	70-72°	..	..	112°	Brown	C ₂₁ H ₁₄ O ₃ N ₄ Br ₃ F	8.28	8.45
12. 2'-Hydroxy-3'-bromo-4-methoxy-Ch (C ₁₆ H ₁₂ O ₃ Br ₃ F)	Yellow	70°	..	..	103°	Orange	C ₂₂ H ₁₆ O ₆ N ₄ Br ₃ F	7.99	8.10
13. 2',2'-Dihydroxy-3'-bromo-Ch (C ₁₅ H ₁₀ O ₃ Br ₃ F)	Yellow	82°	..	..	110°	Do	C ₂₁ H ₁₄ O ₆ N ₄ Br ₃ F	8.10	8.27
14. 2'-Hydroxy-3'-bromo-3,4-methylenedioxy-Ch (C ₁₆ H ₁₀ O ₄ Br ₃ F)	Light yellow	90°	..	..	87-89°	Do	C ₂₂ H ₁₄ O ₇ N ₄ Br ₃ F	7.88	7.94
15. 2',4'-Dihydroxy-3-methoxy-3'-bromo-Ch (C ₁₆ H ₁₂ O ₄ Br ₃ F)	Light orange	74°	..	..	220°	Do	C ₂₂ H ₁₆ O ₇ N ₄ Br ₃ F	7.76	7.92
16. 2'-Hydroxy-3'-bromo-4-dimethylamino-Ch (C ₁₇ H ₁₅ O ₂ NBr ₃ F)	Orange	117°	..	..	127°	Brownish yellow	C ₂₃ H ₁₉ O ₅ N ₅ Br ₃ F	9.62	9.94

* Ch=5'-fluorochalkone.

Reformation of the Chalkone by Debromination.—A mixture of the above dibromide (0.2 g.), KI (0.2 g.), and dry acetone (20-25 ml) was refluxed on a water bath at 65-70° for 2 to 3 hours. The solid, obtained after removal of acetone and pouring the contents in water, was washed with $\text{Na}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_3$ solution (5%) and crystallised from ethanol. In each case the product was identified as the original chalkone by comparison of its m.p. with that of the original chalkone and also by mixed m.p. determination.

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